

Bridging the gap between OLAP and OLTP

Fedor Gorin^a

^a *Equifax Canada Co., North American Centre, 5700 Yonge St, North York, Canada*

Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Traditionally OLAP and OLTP systems were separate platforms with varying capabilities. Over the past decade organizations have been trying to bridge this gap either through appliances (i.e. Oracle Exadata) or through in-house built platforms. Enter Cloudera. Equifax Canada has tackled this problem utilizing the latest and greatest offerings from Cloudera to truly build one platform that can service the requirements of real-time and batch transactions without data replication, always bringing the workload to the data. Equifax Canada currently receives data in batch and real-time from hundreds of suppliers and leverages this data to create valuable insights for its clients across many industries.

2. Aim

Create a single platform capable of handling large amounts of real-time transactions while simultaneously fulfilling large batch requests.

3. Materials And Methods

The Cloudera platform provides a set of products that are extremely well suited to tackle this problem. The specific tools selected from the platform include HBase, Kafka, Spark, Structured Spark Streaming, Solr, Flume, Oozie and Zookeeper.

4. Results

The platform was implemented and is capable of parallel updates both in real time and in batch. Random access of the data is within 20 milliseconds, and the solution is well designed for secure access of data. Encryption is enabled both at rest and in transit leveraging KMS and KTS and all endpoints are protected by TLS.

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5. Conclusions

With recent advancements in the industry, leveraging one platform to manage multiple workloads makes sense. It alleviates the inconsistencies and synchronization issues which emerge from managing multiple platforms and it empowers organizations by enabling one view of all workloads – a uniform reporting and management structure.

6. Keywords

Spark, Hbase, Kafka, Cluster, Structured Spark Streaming.

Author biography

Fedor Gorin Fedor Gorin completed his Bachelor of Computing and Financial Management at University of Waterloo. He received his first exposure to big data platforms at RBC in 2016 where he was implementing an integrated log monitoring platform. He then joined Equifax Canada in 2017 to contribute to its big data solution leveraging the Cloudera platform.